

Variation of Cationic Activity in Colloidal Clays with the Concentration of the Dispersed Phase

A. K. NAG & A. CHATTERJEE

Department of Chemistry, Presidency College, Calcutta

(Received 19 August 1971; revised MSS received 7 June 1972)

The variations of the activity of Cu^{+2} , Co^{+2} , Zn^{+2} , Ni^{+2} , Mn^{+2} and Cr^{+3} ions of clays, saturated with these ions have been determined at various concentrations of clays by means of clay-membrane electrodes. The activities of ions in dilute clay-salts have been found to increase with the increase in clay concentration but the rate becomes slower as the clay concentration increased. This behaviour of base saturated clay suspensions at higher concentration is most probably due to overlapping of the double layers, which causes a decrease in the number of ions registering their activities.

The percentage dissociation of clay-salts has also been calculated from the observed activity and known concentration of ions present in the clays. The percentage dissociation has been found to decrease sharply with the increase in concentration of the clay suspensions, reaches a minimum value and then in some cases increases slightly.

The use of clay membrane electrode as a tool for the determination of cationic activity was started from the work of Marshall¹. Later on Marshall and Chatterjee² using clay membrane electrode measured the variation of metal ion activities in the course of neutralization of acid colloidal clays with hydroxides and oxides of Na, K, NH_4 , Ca, Mg and Ba.

The work with clay membrane electrode was extended by Mitra and Chatterjee³ who from different Indian clays prepared a number of electrodes and with these electrodes they measured the activities of copper, zinc, manganese and cobalt⁴.

Adhikari⁵ using these electrodes measured the activities of a number of metal ions in aqueous solution. He⁶ also attempted to evaluate activity co-efficient of tetramethyl and tetraethyl ammonium iodide in aqueous solution with the help of the clay membrane electrodes.

Cationic activity measurements, reported above, generally refer to the aqueous solution or dilute suspensions and these values are directly applied to investigate the ion exchange behaviour of clays present in soils. The clay, present in soil, is more or less gel-like and hardly assumes a sol-state under the natural conditions. Hence there is little justification in extrapolating information available in dilute solutions to concentrated pastes. With this end in view, Chatterjee^{7,8} carried out activity measurements of Na, K, NH_4 , Ca, Mg and Ba-ions present in clays at various concentrations, of the clay suspensions ranging from a dilute suspension to concentrated paste.

The present enquiry is an extension of the above work with the trace elements usually found present in soil colloids.

EXPERIMENTAL

The clay membrane electrodes used in this work were prepared and standardised by the usual manner as described in earlier paper⁸. The selected membranes, having negligible asymmetry potential, fixed to one end of a pyrex tubing, separated the base saturated clay suspension or pasté and a solution of known ionic activity. The potential difference across the membrane between two tiny calomel electrodes was measured with the help of a Cambridge Potentiometer. The cationic activity was calculated from the E.M.F. of the cell. Hg, Hg₂Cl₂/Ni (Cu or Zn or Mn or Cr or Co) salt solution/Membrane/Ni (Cu or Zn or Mn or Cr or Co), Clay/Hg₂Cl₂, Hg using Nernst relation

$$E = \frac{RT}{nF} \ln \frac{a(\text{solution})}{a(\text{clay})}$$

The different base-saturated clays used in this work e.g., Ni, Cr-, Co-, Mn and Cr-clays were prepared by the same method as described by Nag and Chatterjee in their previous papers^{9,10}. The variation of cationic activity with concentration of the clay-suspension was studied exactly in a manner reported earlier⁸.

The known activity data for the standard electrolytic solutions used here were calculated by a method of extrapolation of the relevant data obtained from the literature.¹¹

The results of a_{Ni} , a_{Cu} , a_{Zn} , a_{Mn} and a_{Cr} determinations together with their percentage dissociation are recorded in Tables 1 to 6.

TABLE 1

Variation of Cu-ion activity with the concentration of clay-suspension
[known Cu⁺² activity = 1.2×10^{-3}]

Clay suspension g/100 g %	Total molal Cu ⁺² conc. in clay (c)	E.M.F. mv	Cu ⁺² Activity of clay (a)	% Dissoc- iation (= $a/c \times 10^2$)
12.63	0.03915	6.5	7.2×10^{-4}	1.84
7.8	0.02418	8.0	6.43×10^{-4}	2.66
4.6	0.01427	14.5	3.87×10^{-4}	2.71
2.23	0.006913	17.5	3.00×10^{-4}	4.33
0.724	0.00224	26.6	1.51×10^{-4}	6.71

TABLE 2

Variation of Zn-ion activity with the concentration of clay-suspension
[known Zn⁺² activity = 1.12×10^{-3}]

Clay suspension g/100 g %	Total molal Zn ⁺² conc. in clay (c)	E.M.F. mv	Zn ⁺² Activity of clay (a)	% Disso- ciation (= $a/c \times 10^2$)
11.0	0.02365	0.75	11.2×10^{-4}	4.735
7.6	0.01634	14.50	3.5×10^{-4}	2.138
4.8	0.01032	18.35	2.67×10^{-4}	2.582
2.8	0.00602	5.00	16.80×10^{-4}	27.860
1.9	0.00408	26.75	1.4×10^{-4}	3.426
0.81	0.001742	31.20	0.98×10^{-4}	5.164

TABLE 3

Variation of Mn-ion activity with the concentration of clay-suspension
 [known Mn^{+2} activity = 1.67×10^{-3}]

Clay suspension g/100 g %	Total molal Mn^{+2} conc. in clay (c)	E.M.F. mv	Mn^{+2} Activity of clay (a)	% Disso- ciation (= $a/c \times 10^2$)
9.22	0.0378	5.25	11.09×10^{-4}	2.934
4.32	0.0177	19.80	3.5×10^{-4}	1.976
3.50	0.01435	12.50	6.3×10^{-4}	4.389
1.78	0.00729	19.40	3.67×10^{-4}	5.029
0.624	0.00256	21.80	3.039×10^{-4}	11.88

TABLE 4

Variation of Ni-ion activity with the concentration of clay-suspension
 [known Ni^{+2} activity = 1.1×10^{-3}]

Clay suspension g/100 g %	Total molal Ni^{+2} conc. in clay (c)	E.M.F. mv	Ni^{+2} Activity of clay (a)	% Disso- ciation (= $a/c \times 10^2$)
12.93	0.03999	8.90	21.9×10^{-4}	5.47
6.82	0.02113	2.20	2.0×10^{-4}	0.9464
4.50	0.01395	8.95	5.4×10^{-4}	3.87
2.50	0.00775	15.00	3.4×10^{-4}	4.387
1.90	0.00589	16.70	3.0×10^{-4}	5.093
0.594	0.001842	11.50	4.30×10^{-4}	23.35

TABLE 5

Variation of Co-ion activity with the concentration of clay-suspension
 [known Co^{+2} activity = 2.3×10^{-3}]

Clay suspension g/100 g %	Total molal Co^{+2} conc. in clay (c)	E.M.F. mv	Co^{+2} Activity of clay (a)	% Disso- ciation (= $a/c \times 10^2$)
11.5	0.0419	7.45	12.88×10^{-4}	3.074
5.1	0.01862	13.45	8.06×10^{-4}	4.329
3.29	0.012008	16.60	6.305×10^{-4}	5.25
1.25	0.00456	28.45	2.51×10^{-4}	5.504
0.5	0.001825	33.20	1.628×10^{-4}	8.921

DISCUSSION

The nature of variation of the activity of Mn^{+2} , Cr^{+3} and Cu^{+2} ions are more or less similar in nature although their initial slopes differ. The initial slope of the curve of Cr^{+3} is maximum. The activity of Ni^{+2} ion in Ni-Clay initially shows a decrease, attains a minimum value at about 2% concentration of the clay and then gradually increases with the increase of clay concentration. The Cu^{+2} and Cr^{+3} ion activity curves flatten as the clay becomes concentrated. In case of Mn^{+2} , Cr^{+3} and Cu^{+2} , the rate of increase of the ion

TABLE 6

Variation of Cr-ion activity with the concentration of clay-suspension
 [known Cr^{+3} activity = 3.38×10^{-4}]

Clay suspension g/100 g %	Total molal Cr^{+3} conc. in clay (c)	E.M.F. mv	Cr^{+3} Activity of clay (a)	% Disso- ciation (= $a/c \times 10^2$)
11.7	0.01638	3.6	2.21×10^{-4}	1.349
7.6	0.01064	4.0	1.09×10^{-4}	1.024
3.14	0.004395	5.15	1.85×10^{-4}	4.209
1.90	0.00266	6.3	1.61×10^{-4}	6.052
0.76	0.001064	14.0	0.66×10^{-4}	6.203

activity decreases as the clay concentration increases which may be due to the overlapping of the double layers as the clay particles come closer to each other, thus causing a decrease in the number of ions registering their activities. The activity curves of Zn^{+2} , Co^{+2} and Ni^{+2} ions are somewhat different in nature. Here the activity values increase steadily without showing practically any tendency to decrease up to the clay concentration studied.

The percentage dissociation has been calculated from the observed activity (a) and the total concentration (c) of the ions present in the respective clays.

The percentage dissociation is found to decrease with increasing concentration of the clay up to a certain extent, then they remain either constant or show a slight increase. The percentage dissociation of these ions present in the base saturated clays, unlike bivalent ions Ca, Mg and Ba, are fairly high and may be compared with those of monovalent ions^{7,8}. Most of these metal ions form co-ordinated compounds with water molecules resulting in heavy hydration of these ions which may, at least, partially prevent overlapping of the double layers, a tendency which was also observed in the activity measurements of the ions Zn^{+2} , Ni^{+2} and Co^{+2} .

REFERENCES

1. C. E. Marshall, *Colloid Chemistry of Silicate Minerals*, Academic Press, 1949.
2. C. E. Marshall and B. Chatterjee, *J. Phys. Coll. Chem.*, 1950, **54**, 671.
3. D. K. Mitra and B. Chatterjee, *J. Indian Soc. Soil. Sci.*, 1953, **1**, 12.
4. D. K. Mitra and B. Chatterjee, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **32**, 751.
5. M. Adhikari, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **44**, 347.
6. M. Adhikari, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **45**, 1083.
7. A. Chatterjee, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **33**, 399.
8. A. Chatterjee, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1960, **37**, 457.
9. A. K. Nag and A. Chatterjee, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **45**, 101.
10. A. K. Nag and A. Chatterjee, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **46**, 393.
11. Robinson and Stokes, "Electrolyte Solutions"—Butterworths Scientific Publications, 1959.